

IMPORTANCE OF THESAURUS DICTIONARIES IN LINGUISTICS

Nabiyeva Parvina Akbarjonovna
Erkin Muhammad Aalim

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8036741>

Abstract. One of the most important and urgent issues facing applied linguistics is the development of Uzbek linguistics and the further increase of the prestige of our native language at the world level. We, the youth, must take this responsibility. After all, our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev says this about the state policy aimed at educating the young generation: "Our young people are independent thinkers, highly intellectual and spiritual we will mobilize all the efforts and capabilities of our country and society so that they can become people who have potential and become happy people who are not idle to their peers on a global scale." The computerization of the Uzbek language, which is a modern science requirement, is being formed based on the world experience.

Key words: Computer linguistics, electronic dictionaries, thesaurus, ideographic thesaurus.

Today, computer lexicography is developing on the basis of various additional possibilities. Initially, computer dictionaries were monolingual and bilingual. Currently, multilingual (thirty, four, six, ten) electronic dictionaries are being created. The first appearance of computer dictionaries was only a general lexicon. Now the dictionaries are being expanded with a base of words related to science, construction, aviation, automotive, military, religious, and legal fields.

There are several types of computer dictionaries. To these we can include glossary dictionaries, concordance dictionaries, glossary dictionaries, thesaurus dictionaries and others.

Thesaurus is a special field of knowledge that should contribute to the correct use of lexical units in a general sense. In modern linguistics, semantic relations between lexical units (synonym, antonym, hyperonym, hyponym, etc.) is a special type of dictionary that represents . This type of dictionary is a database that serves to store information about various relationships between words and phrases..

The term thesaurus is derived from the Greek language and means "treasure". Thesaurus can be used in two different ways:

- 1) dictionaries with complete information based on linguistic analysis;
- 2) a systematized set of information related to a specific field of knowledge in humans or computing machines. The words contained in it are not alphabetized, but rather a linguistic dictionary formed and organized as a set of topics and themes. Thesaurus is a dictionary that includes the lexical-semantic and contextual meanings of a certain word. Dictionaries of this type are considered to be the most effective means of describing certain fields of science. In some sources, the thesaurus is compared to an ideographic (semantic) dictionary. In the ideographic dictionary, the dictionary articles are formed not in the usual alphabetical order

of the glossema (head word), but by its meanings (the lexical meaning of the head word or phrase). While alphabetical dictionaries serve to learn something about a specific word, an ideographic dictionary contains information based on a specific concept, that is, it is shown what words are used to express a specific concept. In such a dictionary, there is no transition from word to understanding (word → understanding), but from understanding to words (understanding → words). The concept of family includes the words father, mother, child, son, daughter, brother, sister, sister. When using the ideographic dictionary, students form and develop the competencies of expressing a certain concept using different words, logical thinking, and mental perception. In fact, the thesaurus covers not only information about reality, but also meta-information (information about information) that makes it possible to receive new information.

Thesaurus is “specially organized information” [2;59], a collection of lexical units of the language in a standardized state.[1;38]Thesaurus represents language units and relationships between them. A thesaurus defines the officially accepted language semantics of a national language, the language of a particular science, or an automated control system. Initially, the thesaurus was also used as a dictionary, where the meaning of the word in the texts was fully explained, and it was considered a monolingual dictionary defined by groups of words divided into sections based on semantics. Currently, monolingual dictionary and thesaurus have similarities and differences. A thesaurus dictionary has a number of advantages over a monolingual dictionary, thesauruses cover a specific word in a comprehensive manner.

Regarding the importance of the thesaurus, linguist S. N. Yusupov said the following: “One of the important importance of the thesaurus is that it normalizes terminology. The problem of identification and elimination of synonymy can be combined in the thesaurus of synonymous or conditionally synonymous words into separate groups (classes) and participate in this direction. is solved with Such a work process will be aimed at performing concrete terminological functions while simplifying the information equipment in the thesaurus. The thesaurus in electronic format is one of the most complete dictionaries of words in every field. It differs from ordinary dictionaries in that it fully explains the essence of each word. In the thesaurus dictionary you can see the embodiment of several dictionary characters. The electronic version of this dictionary saves people's time while getting complete information about a word. In such a dictionary, each word's synonym, antonym, etymology, homonym and a series of words that can be combined with it are covered. A thesaurus is a maximally complete dictionary with annotated words and examples of their use in the text. In modern linguistics, a thesaurus is a lexical unit showing semantic relations between lexical units (synonyms, antonyms, paronyms, hyponyms, antonyms). Thesauruses are mainly created in electronic form and are a means of describing a specific subject area in detail, it is a complete information about a specific subject.

The difference between a thesaurus and an annotated dictionary is that it not only explains a concept, but also increases its relationship to other concepts and groups of concepts actively used in the field of artificial intelligence. Also, the thesaurus is used as a set of all information possessed by the subject in information theory.

Thesaurus makes it possible to collect and organize knowledge. Searching for information sources and information in this system according to their meaning will facilitate the work of not only experts in the field of computer linguistics, but also all representatives of

the information technology field, and increase their level of knowledge. To do this, first of all, we explain the general structure of the thesaurus, the structure of thesaurus sources and the set of relationships between terms. It is necessary to pay attention to the problems of selection and reflection of relations between terms. Also, the thesaurus should ensure the logical integrity of the terminological system. In this regard, researches created in English and Russian computer linguistics serve as a reference source. [3;25]

In a broad sense, a thesaurus appears as a means of describing the system of knowledge about reality possessed by an individual carrier or a group of carriers. This carrier can also perform the task of receiving additional information, as a result of which its thesaurus will also change. In this case, the initial thesaurus determines the receiver's ability to receive semantic information. When studying systems with artificial intelligence in psychology, the characteristics of the thesaurus that are manifested in the process of receiving and understanding information by individuals are studied. In the theories of sociology and communication, the properties of individual and collective thesauruses that provide opportunities for mutual agreement are interpreted based on the generality of the thesaurus. In such situations, it is necessary to include in the thesaurus complex contents and their semantic connections, which define the information reserve of a complex system.

A thesaurus system has been effectively established in several countries. In particular, the thesauri created in Russian linguistics include the following:

1. The relation of the word or language unit to morphology and syntax.
2. Pronunciation.
3. Semantic composition.
 - A) the original meaning of the word;
 - B) synonym;
 - D) antonym;
 - E) hyperonym;
 - F) hyponym.
4. Words with close meaning.
5. Etymology.
6. Use in phraseology.
7. Use in other languages.

Since the vocabulary of a living language is constantly changing, a thesaurus can be built only on the basis of materials from dead languages or predetermined written records. Dictionaries based on collecting the lexicon from certain written monuments (for example, dictionaries compiled in Greek, Latin languages) are considered as such dictionaries.[5;53]

In Turkology, dictionaries compiled on the basis of Turkish written monuments by A.K. Borovkov, E.I. Fozilov, A. Najib have both glossary and thesaurus symbols. Dictionaries compiled according to the language of writers or some of their works are considered a thesaurus; An ideographic dictionary is a dictionary in which lexical units related to a certain field of science are arranged in thematic order and the semantic (species-genus, synonymy, etc.) relations between these units are reflected. In this case, the words are not in alphabetical order, but all the words related to one topic, one concept are given in one place: the necessary words are searched according to the concept.

A thesaurus allows you to avoid word repetition and potential monotony from overuse. They are used to locate common or disappearing words. The language is enriched with the help of alternative vocabulary. [5;81]

In linguistics, thesauruses have the following types of dictionaries:

- Amara - kosha (Amara dictionary) - an early Sanskrit dictionary (III-IV centuries);
- English Thesaurus Roje (XIX century) - includes about 15,000 lexical units;
- Wiktionary is a multilingual, free-to-fill dictionary and thesaurus ("Ruswiktionary" contains 250,000 definitions, 67,000 relations);
- RuTez - thesaurus of the Russian language - (by the Center for Information Research) was created for the purpose of automatic indexing. From 1997 to now, it reflects 45,000 concepts, 107,000 words and expressions, and 177,000 relationships.
- Thesaurus in the dictionary of D.N. Ushakov – A large explanatory dictionary of the modern Russian language (A large explanatory dictionary of the modern Russian language);
- Etymological dictionary of the Russian language. Fasmer Max (Etymological dictionary of the Russian language);
- Translation of the thesaurus into English in the dictionary "Russian-English Physical Dictionary" and others.

The thesaurus is very close to monolingual dictionaries, which define the derivatives of the main parameters of each word. S.I. Ojegov's Russian dictionary is an example of this. In the thesaurus, semantic-meaningful connections between words are represented by antonyms, synonyms, hyponyms, hyperonyms, groups:

- Synonyms - words (combinations) with different spellings and similar meanings: for example: sweet, beautiful.
- Antonyms - words with opposite meanings: good - bad.
- A hyponym is a term that is a special case of another general concept. Officer - hyponym (military); human - hyperonym (military)
- A hyperonym is a term that is common to a number of other personal concepts. Hyponym (she cooks sweet food), hyponym (keeps her house clean), hyponym (knows how to sew) - these characteristics are combined under the hyperonym of a good housewife.

In conclusion, creating a thesaurus in a certain language is a responsible task. A thesaurus is a very complex dictionary in its own right. Therefore, one or two people cannot do it. Creating a thesaurus requires the participation of a dozen or more specialists. Therefore, a creative group consisting of representatives of several fields, such as experts in this field, linguists, logicians, and lexicographers, should be formed. Only then will a thesaurus be created that can meet the needs of the times. When creating a thesaurus, first of all, it is necessary to get acquainted with the thesaurus of "word" (word, slova) available in English and Russian languages, and based on them, select lexemes related to the lexeme of the word in the Uzbek language. It is possible to form a dictionary base in Uzbek based on the thesaurus of vocabulary creation theories and the thesaurus of word lexemes in English and Russian. Also, it is appropriate to carefully study synonymous relationships in the formation of thesaurus.

References:

- 1.Hamroeva Sh.M. A Brief Annotated Glossary of Corpus Linguistics Terms. - Tashkent: "Rainbow" publishing house. - 47 p.;
- 2.Polatov A., Muhammedova S. Computer Linguistics. - Tashkent, 2007.
- 3.Kurbonova F. Thesaurus of state verbs. - Tashkent, 2014.
- 4.Zakharov V.P. Corpus linguistics: Educational method. stipend. / Zakharov V.P. – St. Petersburg, 2005. – p. 48.
- 5.Azarova I.V. Computer thesaurus of the Russian language type WordNet // Computer technology and intellectual technology. Conference Dialog, 2003. / Azarova I.V., Mitrofanova, O.A., Sinopalnikova, A.A. // M., C. 43-50.